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Regeneration of methane splitting catalysts by interfacial hydrogenation

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Abstract:	<p>Methane splitting, also known as decomposition or pyrolysis, has a unique potential to accelerate the transition from the current carbon-based economy towards the foreseen hydrogen economy. Low-temperature catalytic methane splitting systems are unavailable due to fast catalyst deactivation, caused by solid carbon that encapsulates the catalyst. Catalyst regeneration must be performed to reactivate the catalyst and achieve a long-term operational lifetime. This can be accomplished by cyclically refeeding a portion of the produced hydrogen back to the catalyst, which promotes the hydrogenation of carbon atoms, preferentially at the interface between carbon deposits and catalytic nanoparticles. Interfacial hydrogenation ideally breaks the bonds that connect carbon allotrope products to the metal catalyst, causing the former to detach, and freeing the catalytic metal surface for further reaction. In this work, a proof-of-concept of this technology is provided, showing the full regeneration of a bulk-type Ni catalyst during 22 cycles of methane splitting, at 550 °C and 1 bar. Furthermore, a commercial SiO₂-Al₂O₃-supported Ni catalyst has been used to study the regenerability of a highly active nanostructured material by interfacial hydrogenation, using different reactor designs. It has been demonstrated that regeneration is beneficial to improve the stability of Ni-based systems, at the applied working conditions. Nevertheless, tip-grown carbon nanotubes were considered as a cause of permanent deactivation, which could not be solved by refeeding hydrogen into the system.</p>
Response to Reviewers:	<p>Chemical Engineering Journal Manuscript ID: CEJ-D-24-12125 TITLE: Regeneration of methane splitting catalysts by interfacial hydrogenation</p> <p>Introductory comment The authors are thankful for the time and useful comments from the Reviewers and the Editor and the opportunity to improve our initial manuscript. All the Reviewers' comments were carefully considered, and the corresponding changes were implemented in the revised marked-up version. In the following pages, we present a point-by-point reply to the Reviewers' comments. For a better understanding, the Reviewers' comments were colored in black, our comments/responses were colored in red, and the added text to the manuscript was colored in blue.</p> <p>Point-by-point response to the Reviewers' reports</p>

Highlights

- Catalytic methane decomposition is critically hindered by C growth;
- Interfacial C hydrogenation allows CO_x-free regeneration of deactivated catalysts;
- C growth mechanism may affect catalyst structure irreversibly;
- Control over C growth mechanisms is required to design fully regenerable systems.

Regeneration of methane splitting catalysts by interfacial hydrogenation

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Abstract

Methane splitting, also known as decomposition or pyrolysis, has a unique potential to accelerate the transition from the current carbon-based economy towards the foreseen hydrogen economy. Low-temperature catalytic methane splitting systems are unavailable due to fast catalyst deactivation, caused by solid carbon that encapsulates the catalyst. Catalyst regeneration must be performed to reactivate the catalyst and achieve a long-term operational lifetime. This can be accomplished by cyclically refeeding a portion of the produced hydrogen back to the catalyst, which promotes the hydrogenation of carbon atoms, preferentially at the interface between carbon deposits and catalytic nanoparticles. Interfacial hydrogenation ideally breaks the bonds that connect carbon allotrope products to the metal catalyst, causing the former to detach, and freeing the catalytic metal surface for further reaction. In this work, a proof-of-concept of this technology is provided, showing the full regeneration of a bulk-type Ni catalyst during 22 cycles of methane splitting, at 550 °C and 1 bar. Furthermore, a commercial SiO₂-Al₂O₃-supported Ni catalyst has been used to study

30 the regenerability of a highly active nanostructured material by interfacial
31 hydrogenation, using different reactor designs. It has been demonstrated that
32 regeneration is beneficial to improve the stability of Ni-based systems, at the applied
33 working conditions. Nevertheless, tip-grown carbon nanotubes were considered as a
34 cause of permanent deactivation, which could not be solved by refeeding hydrogen
35 into the system.

36 *Keywords:* methane splitting, stability, catalyst regeneration, CO_x-free hydrogen,
37 carbon

38

39 Word count: 5400 words

40 **Abbreviations:**

41	GHG	greenhouse gases
42	CMS	catalytic methane splitting
43	XRD	x-ray diffractometry
44	XPS	x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy
45	TEM	transmission electron microscopy
46	BE	binding energy
47	MWCNT	multi-walled carbon nanotube

48 **Nomenclature:**

49	X_{CH_4}	methane conversion	
50	x_{H_2}	hydrogen molar fraction	
51	x_{CH_4}	methane molar fraction	
52	a_{H_2}	hydrogen production activity	$\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{Ni}}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$
53	W	catalyst mass	g_{Ni}
54	\dot{m}_{H_2}	hydrogen mass flow	$\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$

55	ρ_{H_2}	hydrogen NPT density	$\text{g}_{\text{H}_2}\cdot\text{ml}^{-1}$
56	$F_{\text{CH}_4,\text{in}}$	methane inlet flow	$\text{ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$
57	F_{H_2}	hydrogen flow	$\text{ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$
58	X_{H_2}	hydrogen conversion	
59	d	average crystal size	nm
60	k	crystallite shape factor	
61	λ	wavelength	nm
62	β	full width at half maximum	rad
63	θ	diffraction angle	rad
64	$t_{\text{methane splitting}}$	methane splitting time	h
65	$\frac{I_{\text{D}}}{I_{\text{G}}}$	ratio between D and G bands	

66 **1. Introduction**

67 With global warming, weather patterns have been changing, threatening life
68 equilibrium on Earth [1]. Simultaneously, energy demand worldwide keeps increasing,
69 driven by emerging economies, further complicating the abandonment of fossil fuels
70 [2]. Energy from renewable sources currently stands as the most accepted substitute
71 for carbon-based energy, with a few countries already producing most of their
72 electricity from this route, and many more implementing extensive programs to do so
73 [3]. Nonetheless, the intermittent nature of some renewable energy sources rushes the
74 development of energy storage solutions. Also, a considerable share of energy demand
75 is derived from applications with low levels of electrification, such as heavy and long-

76 haul transportation, and metallurgical and cement industries, requiring the use of fuels
77 (generally of fossil origin) [4]. To address these challenges, electricity must be
78 converted into other energy vectors. Hydrogen is a promising chemical energy vector
79 and can be produced while assisting the fluctuation of renewable electricity through
80 processes such as water electrolysis, thus aiding in balancing the electrical grid [5].
81 Renewable hydrogen (*green* hydrogen) can be used as an alternative fuel to replace
82 fossil fuels, in applications in which full electrification is more challenging or
83 ineffective [4]. This marks the basis of the so-called hydrogen economy, in which
84 hydrogen would be used directly in fuel cells and hydrogen turbines or indirectly in
85 reverse petrochemistry, and for producing synthetic fuels.

86 Currently, most of the produced hydrogen, *ca.* 96 %, is produced via the steam
87 reforming of fossil carbon resources, most often natural gas (*grey* hydrogen) and coal
88 (*black* hydrogen) [6]. Besides hydrogen, these processes produce CO₂ as a by-product,
89 currently adding up to 830 MtCO₂·yr⁻¹ globally [7]. To allow true decarbonization of
90 the energy sector, hydrogen production must avoid the emission of greenhouse gases
91 (GHG). Water electrolysis is often considered, as it can use renewable electricity for
92 splitting water into hydrogen (*green* hydrogen) and oxygen. Although electrolysis
93 presents many environmental advantages, *green* hydrogen production remains
94 ineffective and the associated capital and operational costs are yet uncompetitive with
95 the reforming of fossil fuels [8,9]. Therefore, alternative processes to produce clean
96 hydrogen must be developed. To this end, technologies exploiting fossil fuels for
97 hydrogen production, whilst avoiding CO₂ emissions, have been conceptualized and
98 developed [10]. Considering the current outlook, methane splitting, also known as
99 decomposition or pyrolysis, is a particularly relevant alternative to the current state-of-

100 the-art, allowing a soft transition of energy systems [11]. Methane splitting is an
101 endothermic reaction, in which carbon-hydrogen bonds are cleaved, with the loose
102 atoms reorganizing as hydrogen molecules and solid carbon allotropes, equation (1):

103 Methane splitting produces high-purity *turquoise* hydrogen, free from CO₂ or other
104 GHG. Solid carbon is produced instead, which is much more stable and easier to
105 handle. Besides, the carbon product may contribute decisively to the economic
106 viability of the process, as carbon materials have well-established, as well as emerging,
107 commercial applications. From a thermodynamic perspective, methane pyrolysis can
108 be carried out at above *ca.* 450 °C; however, its high activation energy makes kinetics
109 reasonable only for temperatures above *ca.* 1300 °C [12]. Since processes at such high
110 temperatures suffer from material, wear and have poor energy efficiency due to high
111 energy losses, their industrial implementation is hampered due to prohibitive costs.
112 Catalytic methane splitting (CMS) considers the use of catalysts to reduce the
113 temperature for reaction. Metal catalysts, with Ni, Fe, and Co are considered the most
114 active for the decomposition of methane at milder operating temperatures (450-700 °C)
115 [13,14]. CMS using natural gas is currently very advantageous, as it allows the
116 production of clean hydrogen with comparable estimated costs to the reforming
117 process [15–17]. The use of metal catalysts also promotes the formation of graphitic
118 carbon materials [18,19], which have much higher commercial value, due to their
119 unique properties, in applications such as electrode components, bipolar plates, rubber,
120 construction or asphalt precursors [20].

121 Natural gas splitting does not cause direct CO₂ emissions, but natural gas
122 exploitation may originate CO₂ emissions. However, methane splitting can also be
123 performed using biomethane from anaerobic biomass digestion. Biomass production
124 consumes atmospheric CO₂. Consequently, biomethane splitting is capable of
125 effectively transforming atmospheric CO₂ and H₂O into H₂, solid carbon and organic
126 fertilizers (by-products of anaerobic digestion). This is a step beyond *green* hydrogen,
127 as such, the coinage of a new shade denotation is proposed by the authors - *bright*
128 hydrogen, which denotes hydrogen produced with net negative CO₂ emissions.

129 As of now, CMS is critically hindered by carbon accumulation, which ends
130 up clogging the catalyst active sites, halting the process [21]. To avoid such
131 deactivation, cyclic carbon detachment from the catalyst must be promoted
132 (regeneration). Several methods to regenerate CMS catalysts have been proposed over
133 the past decades, such as mechanical detachment [22,23], carbon oxidation with O₂
134 [24,25] or with CO₂ [26,27] and carbon gasification with water [28]. However,
135 mechanical detachment tends to be either ineffective [29] or to require interruptions
136 during continuous processes [30], which ends up damaging the catalyst particles.
137 Oxidation of carbon deposits produces CO₂ and/or CO, denying the environmental
138 advantages of CMS. Moreover, the oxidation state of metal catalysts may also be
139 affected, requiring subsequent surface reductions to resume their catalytic
140 performance. Consequently, despite the environmental and economic potential of
141 CMS, it still requires an effective and CO₂-free regeneration step, which further avoids
142 disruptions of continuous process or loss of catalyst active sites. Interfacial carbon
143 hydrogenation addresses this crucial need: if carbon is selectively hydrogenated at the
144 carbon-metal interface, the carbon allotrope will detach off the catalyst, without any

145 damage to the active sites or CO_x production. Temperatures below *ca.* 750 °C are
146 preferred to selectively confine carbon hydrogenation to its interface with the
147 hydrogen-activating metal, since reaction rates of non-catalytic methane splitting are
148 very low at such temperatures. This allows catalyst regeneration with a fraction of the
149 produced H₂ [31,32].

150 In the present work, cyclic hydrogenative regeneration is tested at 550 °C and
151 1 bar; at these conditions, the equilibrium conversions of the methane splitting reaction
152 and of that of the reverse reaction are nearly equal, *i.e. ca.* 50 % [33]. Ni-based
153 catalysts were used, depositing them on planar and tubular ceramic substrates, sealed
154 inside in-house developed slab reactors. To promote catalyst regeneration, the methane
155 feed to the reactors was periodically ceased, and replaced with pure hydrogen, to
156 cyclically favor the carbon hydrogenative gasification reaction and consequently
157 regenerate the catalysts [20].

158 **2. Materials and methods**

159 *2.1 Catalytic layer preparation*

160 Two Ni-based powder catalysts, *i.e.* massive (bulk) NiO and a supported
161 Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ were coated as a thin layer on α -Al₂O₃ porous planar and tubular
162 membranes, as well as steel tubes, as substrates and sealed slab reactors, depicted in
163 Figure 1. α -Al₂O₃ circular planar membranes with *ca.* 3.44 cm diameter and 0.15 cm
164 thickness were purchased from Kerafol. α -Al₂O₃ tubular membranes with 5 cm width,
165 1.05 cm external diameter, and 0.16 cm wall thickness (0.73 cm internal diameter)

166 were purchased from Inopor. Steel tubes with 0.95 cm external diameter (3/8 inch
167 standard size), 0.70 cm internal diameter, and 10 cm width were purchased from
168 Swagelok. NiO powder, 400 mesh, Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ (62 wt.% of Ni and 4:1 SiO₂/Al₂O₃
169 ratio), and α -terpineol (CH₃C₆H₈C(CH₃)₂OH) were purchased from Alfa Aesar,
170 Merck, and Acros Organics, respectively. To produce the coatings, NiO and Ni/SiO₂-
171 Al₂O₃ were mixed in α -terpineol and milled for 1 h at 300 rpm, using a Retsch PM 100
172 ball miller, until homogeneous viscous emulsions formed.

174 **Figure 1** – Reactor designs employed to study interfacial regeneration of methane splitting
 175 catalysts, adapted from [34]. A) Planar reactor, where a1 is the α -Al₂O₃ porous planar substrate,
 176 a2 is the Ni catalyst layer, a3 is the methane inlet, a4 is the hydrogen inlet, and a5 is the outlet.
 177 B) Tubular reactor coated on the inner wall, where b1 is the steel tube, b2 is the Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃

178 catalyst layer, b3 is the inlet, and b4 is the outlet. C) Tubular membrane reactor, where c1 is the
179 α -Al₂O₃ tubular substrate, c2 is the Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst layer, c3 is the methane inlet, c4 is
180 the hydrogen inlet, and c5 is the outlet.
181

182 A RokuPrint RP 2.2 screen-printer was used to apply a 2 x 2 cm² square NiO
183 coating on top of an α -Al₂O₃ planar membrane; the process was performed at ambient
184 temperature and pressure. The used emulsion was made by mixing NiO powder in α -
185 terpineol until a 70 wt.% solid content was reached. The screen-printed substrates
186 were then dried overnight at 200 °C for evaporating the solvent and ensuring a
187 homogeneous catalyst layer. Dip-coating was used to coat Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ on the outer
188 area of the α -Al₂O₃ tubular membranes, as well as on the inner area of the steel tubes.
189 Dip-coating was performed by dipping the selected substrate into the Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃
190 emulsion, for 10 s. The emulsion was prepared by mixing Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ powder in
191 α -terpineol until a solid mass content of 30 wt.% was reached. The dip-coated
192 substrates were then dried overnight at 200 °C, under constant rotation, evaporating
193 the solvent and ensuring homogeneous catalyst layers.

194 2.2 Activity and regenerability evaluation

195 Prior to methane splitting tests, the catalyst layers were subjected to a
196 reduction activation treatment, *in situ*, by mixing 50 % hydrogen in nitrogen, at 550 °C
197 and 1 bar, for 1 h to render nickel into its metallic form. To test activity and
198 regenerability through interfacial hydrogenation, pure methane was fed to the catalyst
199 layers, with periodic cyclic feeding of pure hydrogen. The planar membrane was sealed
200 with vermiculite foils (Thermiculite 866 from Flexitallic) in a two-chamber cell
201 reactor, as depicted in Figure 1 A – Planar reactor. 5 ml·min⁻¹ of methane were

202 cyclically fed to the catalyst side of the membrane, while $5 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of hydrogen were
203 fed from the opposite side during regeneration. This initial experiment was performed
204 to assess the potential of active site regeneration by hydrogenation, as bulk-Ni catalyst
205 tends to rapidly deactivate due to widespread carbon formation. Wall-coated steel
206 tubes were sealed with Swagelok steel fittings to the test set-up, as depicted in Figure
207 1 B – Wall-coated tubular reactor. $20 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of methane were fed to evaluate
208 splitting, while $20 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of hydrogen were fed instead during regeneration.
209 Experiments using wall-coated tubular reactors were designed to understand the
210 benefits of hydrogen-based regeneration on the loosening of carbon materials from the
211 catalytic surface, which causes deactivation due to clogging of the reactor. As bulk-Ni
212 typically presents lower activities and faster deactivation compared to supported
213 catalysts, the Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst was applied in this case to ensure higher reaction
214 rates, leading to greater carbon formation rates. Tubular membranes were sealed with
215 glass paste (GL1729 glass paste from MO-SCI Specialty Products) inside a steel
216 cylinder reactor with a 2.65 cm internal diameter (large volume for carbon growth),
217 via a dense α -Al₂O₃ tube, which can be used to feed gas to the inner volume of the
218 porous tubular membranes, as depicted in Figure 1 C – Tubular membrane reactor.
219 During splitting steps $100 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of methane were supplied via one of the ends of
220 the tubular membrane reactor, while $50 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ of hydrogen were fed through the
221 inner volume of the membranes for regeneration, in alternation with methane feed. The
222 tubular membrane reactor was also applied to test the Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst as a
223 means to evaluate the overall yield of regeneration.

224 Reference experiments were conducted by continuously feeding methane
225 until deactivation. The catalyst was considered deactivated when the catalytic activity

226 dropped below 20 % of its initial performance value, or until operation pressure built
 227 up to the point where the set inlet gas flow could not be maintained (*ca.* 5 bar).
 228 Regenerability experiments were conducted by cyclically subjecting the catalytic
 229 systems to steps of production/splitting (pure methane) and regeneration (pure
 230 hydrogen), interspersed with inert purges (pure nitrogen). These purge steps were
 231 performed to avoid a mixture between hydrogen produced during splitting and
 232 hydrogen fed during regeneration, thereby enabling independent quantification of
 233 hydrogen production and consumption rates. All tests were performed at 550 °C and
 234 atmospheric pressure. Outlet gas streams were analyzed by on-line gas
 235 chromatography in 3 min intervals, in an Agilent 990Micro gas chromatograph (GC)
 236 with a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Gas separation in the GC was achieved
 237 with a 10 m Molsieve column, using Ar as carrier gas. Catalytic performance was
 238 evaluated through both methane conversion and hydrogen production activity,
 239 assuming ideal gas behavior for all gases at the described operating conditions, using
 240 equations (2) and (3), respectively:

$$X_{\text{CH}_4} = \frac{x_{\text{H}_2}}{x_{\text{H}_2} + 2x_{\text{CH}_4}} \quad (2)$$

$$a_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{H}_2}}{W} = 60 \frac{F_{\text{H}_2} \rho_{\text{H}_2}}{W} = 60 \frac{2F_{\text{CH}_4, \text{in}} X_{\text{CH}_4} \rho_{\text{H}_2}}{W} \quad (3)$$

241 where X_{CH_4} is methane conversion, x_{H_2} is hydrogen molar (volumetric) fraction, x_{CH_4}
 242 is methane molar (volumetric) fraction, a_{H_2} is hydrogen production activity in
 243 $\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{g}_{\text{Ni}}^{-1} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, \dot{m}_{H_2} is the mass flowrate of produced hydrogen in $\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$, W is catalyst
 244 (Ni) mass in g_{Ni} , F_{H_2} is the produced hydrogen volume flow at normal pressure and
 245 temperature (NPT) conditions in $\text{ml} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$, ρ_{H_2} is the density of hydrogen at NPT

246 conditions in $\text{g}_{\text{H}_2} \cdot \text{ml}^{-1}$, and $F_{\text{CH}_4, \text{in}}$ is the methane inlet volume flow at NPT conditions
247 in $\text{ml} \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$.

248 Regenerability was evaluated by comparing catalytic performance from cycle
249 to cycle. Hydrogen conversion during regeneration was also assessed to measure the
250 effective hydrogen consumption during regeneration, and calculated according to
251 equation (4) as follows:

$$X_{\text{H}_2} = \frac{2x_{\text{CH}_4}}{x_{\text{H}_2} + 2x_{\text{CH}_4}} \quad (4)$$

252 where X_{H_2} is hydrogen conversion. The deductions of equations (2) and (4) can be
253 consulted in the “Supplementary material”. Splitting step time was set considering the
254 duration of the initial experiments, without regeneration. Regeneration step time was
255 set according to the extension of the splitting cycle, aiming to use *ca.* 10 % of the
256 hydrogen produced in the initial cycle of methane splitting. Nitrogen purge flowrates
257 were set to $20 \text{ ml} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$ for planar membranes and wall-coated tubes, and $100 \text{ ml} \cdot \text{min}^{-1}$
258 for tubular membranes. 20 min of purging was considered as a reasonable duration to
259 fully prevent hydrogen or methane contaminations between cycles, as methane and
260 hydrogen concentrations after these 20 min became lower than the chromatographic
261 quantification limit.

262 2.3 *Structural and physicochemical characterization*

263 To allow their characterization, spent catalyst powder samples were prepared
264 by physically scrapping-off the catalytic layers, and forcefully removing the catalyst

265 from the deposition substrate. Carbon samples were analyzed “as produced” or were
266 milled into fine powder.

267 The crystal structure of pristine (or fresh) and *spent* catalysts, as well as
268 produced carbon structures, was studied with X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, in a
269 Diffractometer Rigaku Smartlab. Powder samples were irradiated with 1.5406 Å
270 monochromatic radiation, from a Cu $K\alpha$ source, at angles (2θ) between 20° and 80°,
271 with a step of 0.02°. The resulting diffractograms were compared with database
272 standards (ICDD), allowing the identification of the crystal phases present in each
273 sample. Average crystal size was assessed through Scherrer Equation, equation (5):

$$d = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (5)$$

274 where d is the average crystal size in nm, k is crystallite shape factor (adimensional),
275 λ is the wavelength of the diffracted X-rays in nm, β is the full width at half maximum
276 in rad, and θ is the diffraction angle in rad. k was given a set value of 0.94 for the
277 characterized materials.

278 The near-surface speciation of pristine and spent catalysts as well as the
279 carbon products resulting from the catalytic processes were studied by X-ray
280 Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS) using a SPECS spectrometer equipped with a
281 Phoibos 150 MCD-9 detector and a non-monochromatic Al $K\alpha$ (1486.6 eV) X-ray
282 source. The XPS spectra were collected under a vacuum pressure of 10⁻⁹ mbar,
283 employing a pass energy of 30 eV and an X-ray power output of 100 W. Data
284 processing involved the utilization of CASA XPS software, with Shirley-type
285 background correction. To establish binding energy (BE) values accurately, calibration

286 was performed relative to the C1s core level of adventitious surface carbon, set at 284.5
287 eV.

288 The crystallography of the carbon products was studied by Raman
289 spectroscopy. A Witec alpha300 spectroscope was used, which irradiated carbon
290 samples with a 532 nm monochromatic laser, at a constant power of 0.5 W.

291 The nanoscale structure of carbon filaments after methane splitting
292 experiments was studied by means of Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) in a
293 JEOL JEM2100F microscope operating at 200kV. Prior to observation, powdered
294 samples were gently dry-cast onto 300 mesh Cu grids coated with a lacey carbon film.
295 Subsequently, the particles were delicately distributed and dispersed across the grid's
296 surface, and any weakly bonded material was eliminated using an air blower. Notably,
297 no mechanical grinding or solvent dispersion techniques were employed, as this was
298 done to preserve the pristine contact between the metal species and the carbon
299 filaments at the nanoscale level.

300 **3. Results and discussion**

301 **3.1 Activity and regenerability experiments**

302 Three reactor designs, described in depth elsewhere [34], were used to assess
 303 catalyst regeneration. The first is a planar reactor – Figure 1A – where unsupported Ni
 304 catalytic particles were coated onto an α -Al₂O₃ circular porous planar substrate. The
 305 second is a tubular reactor – Figure 1B – where the supported Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst
 306 was coated on the inner wall of the reaction zone. The third is a tubular membrane
 307 reactor – Figure 1C – where an α -Al₂O₃ tubular porous ceramic membrane was used
 308 to host the supported Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst, coated in its external surface; this tubular
 309 membrane was closed at one of its ends. Five experiments were performed, namely
 310 one cyclic regeneration experiment in the planar reactor – Experiment 1; two
 311 experiments (continuous – Experiment 2 – and with cyclic regeneration – Experiment
 312 3) in the wall-coated tubular reactor; and two experiments (continuous – Experiment
 313 4 – and with cyclic regeneration – Experiment 5) in the tubular membrane reactor, as
 314 described in Table 1. A process scheme, with detailed cyclic reaction parameters can
 315 be consulted in the “Supplementary material” – Figure S. 1.

316 **Table 1** – The reactors' main characteristics and the corresponding catalytic
 317 activity and stability.

<i>Experiment</i>	<i>Material</i>	<i>Reactor</i>	<i>Deposition</i>	<i>Area</i> <i>reactor</i> <i>cm</i> <i>m</i> ²	<i>Loading</i> <i>mg</i> <i>cm</i> ⁻²	<i>Peak activity</i> <i>gH₂·gNi⁻¹·h⁻¹</i>	<i>Time on stream</i> <i>h</i>	<i>Total H₂ production</i> <i>gH₂·gNi⁻¹</i>	<i>Product</i> <i>g</i>
Experiment 1 <i>Cyclic</i>	Ni-bulk	Planar (A)	Screen-printing	4	10	0.08	4.8	0.20	

Experiment 2 <i>Continuous</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	Wall-coated Tubular (B)	Dip-coating	2 2	10	0.17	14	2.3
Experiment 3 <i>Cyclic</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	Wall-coated Tubular (B)	Dip-coating	2 2	10	0.17	19	3.0
Experiment 4 <i>Continuous</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	Tubular Membrane (C)	Dip-coating	1 6.5	19	1.0	50	32
Experiment 5 <i>Cyclic</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ -Al ₂ O ₃	Tubular Membrane (C)	Dip-coating	1 6.5	19	1.0	100	40

318

319 *Planar reactor using unsupported nickel catalyst deposited on an alumina substrate*

320 The bulk-type NiO catalyst was coated on the α -Al₂O₃ circular porous
321 substrate to reach a loading of 10 mg·cm⁻² (40 mg applied over a square area of
322 2 x 2 cm²). The reaction, Experiment 1, was performed by feeding pure methane
323 (5 ml·min⁻¹) to the reactor running at 550 °C. Figure 2A shows the history of hydrogen
324 productivity for a production stage of 22 cycles. Each cycle comprises four stages: i)
325 a hydrogen production phase of 15 min; ii) an initial purge stage of 20 min with a
326 nitrogen feed of 20 ml·min⁻¹; iii) a regeneration stage of 1 min with a hydrogen feed of
327 5 ml·min⁻¹; iv) a second purge stage of 20 min with nitrogen feed of 20 ml·min⁻¹,
328 similar to the first purge stage. The total specific net production of hydrogen was
329 0.20 g_{H2}·g_{Ni}⁻¹ (0.60 g_C·g_{Ni}⁻¹). Figure 2A shows that the catalyst deactivates quickly, but
330 hydrogen productivity is restored after each regeneration step. The regeneration steps
331 consumed *ca.* 6.3 % of the total hydrogen production.

333 **Figure 2** – Comparison between experiments with (lighter colors) and without (darker colors)
 334 cyclic regeneration processes, regarding hydrogen productivity from methane splitting, as a
 335 function of time, on different reactor designs: A – unsupported Ni catalyst deposited on an
 336 α -Al₂O₃ planar membrane (planar reactor). B – supported Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ deposited on the inner
 337 wall of a tubular reactor (wall-coated tubular reactor). C – supported Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalytic
 338 coating deposited on the outer wall of a cylindrical α -Al₂O₃ membrane (tubular membrane
 339 reactor). The methane conversion values obtained are represented in the secondary vertical axis.
 340 Only the production steps of each cycle are displayed.

341

342 *Wall-coated tubular reactors using supported Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst deposited on the*

343 *inner wall*

344 The inner walls of two tubular reactors were coated with the supported
345 Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst to reach an area-specific catalyst loading of 10 mg·cm⁻². The
346 first wall-coated tubular reactor was continuously fed with 20 ml·min⁻¹ of methane,
347 Experiment 2. Compared to the planar reactor (Experiment 1- loaded with unsupported
348 Ni), the catalyst in this reactor shows much higher stability, *i.e.* *ca.* 14 h of constant
349 hydrogen productivity – *cf.* Figure 2B. In the planar reactor, each cycle endures for
350 only 15 min, requiring regeneration afterwards. The first wall-coated tubular reactor,
351 Experiment 2, produced a total of 7.7 l of hydrogen, corresponding to 2.3 g_{H2}·g_{Ni}⁻¹
352 (6.9 g_C·g_{Ni}⁻¹), *ca.* 10-fold higher than that attained in Experiment 1 (0.20 g_{H2}·g_{Ni}⁻¹)
353 despite the cyclic regeneration. It must be emphasized that the tubular reactor needed
354 to be shut down because of the clogging of the gas flow paths after carbon
355 accumulation, *cf.* Figure 3.

356 The second wall-coated tubular reactor was used to perform a cyclic methane
357 splitting test, Experiment 3. Each cycle also comprehends four stages: i) a hydrogen
358 production stage of 30 min with a methane feed of 20 ml·min⁻¹; ii) a first purge stage
359 of 20 min with a nitrogen feed of 20 ml·min⁻¹; iii) a regeneration stage of 3 min with
360 hydrogen feed of 20 ml·min⁻¹; and iv) a second purge stage of 20 min with nitrogen
361 feed of 20 ml·min⁻¹, matching the first purge stage. The production stage of this reactor
362 is plotted in Figure 2B, showing 19 h of production time, until the complete clogging
363 of the gas flow cross-section by carbon: 5 h more than Experiment 2, without cyclic
364 regeneration. During the operation time, Experiment 3 achieved a net specific
365 production of 3.0 g_{H2}·g_{Ni}⁻¹ (9.1 g_C·g_{Ni}⁻¹); deactivation occurs due to reactor clogging
366 as observed for the continuous experiment - Figure 3.

367

368

Figure 3 - Steel tube reactor clogged by carbon by-product.

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370 *Tubular membrane reactor using supported Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst deposited on the*
371 *outer wall of the tubular membrane*

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The limited operation time in continuous mode discussed above for wall-coated tubular reactors was not a consequence of catalyst stability but rather the reactor design, which did not allow the carbon produced to leave the reaction zone at a sufficient pace. The tubular membrane reactor design aims to address this challenge. It comprehends a porous ceramic tube, coated externally with Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃, to reach an area-specific catalyst loading of 19 mg·cm⁻², and inserted in a tubular shell, as illustrated in Figure 1C. This design allows the formed carbon layers to peel out during the regeneration stage. Two experiments were performed: in the first one, Experiment 4, methane was fed continuously at 100 ml·min⁻¹ to the reactor until deactivation was observed, while in the second, Experiment 5, a cyclic regeneration protocol was

382 applied. In the regeneration experiment, the reactor was operated cyclically,
383 comprehending four stages: i) a hydrogen production stage of 240 min with a methane
384 feed of $100 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$; ii) a first purge stage of 20 min with a nitrogen feed of
385 $100 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$; iii) a regeneration stage of 10 min with a hydrogen feed of $50 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$;
386 and iv) a second purge stage of 20 min with nitrogen feed of $100 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$, as for the
387 first purge stage. The history of the hydrogen productivity for both tests is presented
388 in Figure 2C.

389 Without regeneration, in Experiment 4, the catalyst reached complete
390 deactivation after *ca.* 50 h of operation, where *ca.* 70 l of hydrogen was produced,
391 corresponding to $32 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{Ni}}^{-1}$ ($95 \text{ g}_{\text{C}}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{Ni}}^{-1}$). The use of a cyclic regeneration in
392 Experiment 5 allowed the extension of the catalyst lifetime from 50 h to 100 h, where
393 *ca.* 90 l of net hydrogen was produced along 25 cycles, corresponding to $40 \text{ g}_{\text{H}_2}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{Ni}}^{-1}$
394 (specific carbon production of $120 \text{ g}_{\text{C}}\cdot\text{g}_{\text{Ni}}^{-1}$). Figure 4 shows the hydrogen produced
395 and consumed (regeneration) per cycle throughout the 25 cycles of Experiment 5. The
396 average fraction of hydrogen used for regenerating the catalyst, over the produced
397 hydrogen, is *ca.* 23 %. The tubular membrane reactor design overcame the clogging
398 problem of the previous design (wall-coated tubular reactors), making the catalyst
399 lifetime the main operation bottleneck. It can also be concluded that the cyclic
400 regeneration operation allows extending the lifetime of the catalyst. However, this
401 deactivation must be understood for improving the catalyst stability, which will be
402 studied in the next sections.

404 **Figure 4** – Total NPT hydrogen volume produced in each splitting step (blue circles) of
 405 Experiment 5 (cyclic regeneration in the tubular membrane reactor) compared to total NPT
 406 hydrogen volume consumed in each regeneration step (red squares). The secondary vertical axis
 407 represents the average hydrogen production activity values obtained during the splitting step
 408 (blue circles).

409 3.2 Characterization of catalysts and produced carbon

410 XRD analysis was carried out to identify and characterise the crystalline
 411 structures present in the used Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalytic layers recovered from the tubular
 412 membrane reactor (Figure 1C), as well as the detached carbon flakes. Figure 5A
 413 displays the complete diffractograms (20° to 80°) of the spent catalyst, without and
 414 with cyclic regeneration – Experiments 4 and 5, respectively. Both diffractograms
 415 were dominated by reflexes ascribed to the α -Al₂O₃ phase (ICDD 00-005-0712) which
 416 was extracted from the substrate and mixed with the catalytic layer during the recovery
 417 of the latter by scrapping-off. Residual graphitic carbon crystals (at *ca.* 26.2°, ICDD

418 00-058-1638), and metallic Ni⁰ *fcc* phase (ICDD 00-004-0850), with no detectable
419 NiO, were observed in both samples, respectively Figure 5B and Figure 5C. Applying
420 the Scherrer Equation, the average crystallite size of the Ni particles was assessed. In
421 both the experiments, without and with cyclic regeneration, the Ni phase displays
422 average crystallite size of *ca.* 16 nm. Two samples were also collected from the
423 detached carbon flakes, one from Experiment 4 (reactor without cyclic regeneration)
424 and other from Experiment 5 (reactor with cyclic regeneration); they were milled to
425 produce fine powders, which were then analysed by XRD. As seen in Figure 5D, *fcc*
426 Ni⁰ crystals (ICDD 00-004-0850) are identified in both carbon samples (ICDD 00-058-
427 1638), indicating that Ni particles moved away from the catalytic layer. This suggests
428 the existence of a carbon tip-growth mechanism, which lifts the catalytic metal
429 nanocrystals from the substrate support [20]. The peak catalytic activity of each step
430 of Experiment 5 observed in Figure 2C is mostly constant, which may indicate that the
431 detachment of metal nanoparticles from the catalyst layer does not result in irreversible
432 deactivation, *i.e.* they remain available and active for methane splitting. However, the
433 gradually faster deactivation rate observed within each production cycle suggests that
434 these particles are quickly encapsulated by the carbon deposits.

436 **Figure 5** – XRD diffractograms of spent catalyst samples from tubular membrane reactors (a-c)
 437 and of the produced carbon samples (d), from experiments without and with cyclic regeneration,
 438 respectively Experiment 4 (dark blue line) and Experiment 5 (light blue line): a – complete spent
 439 catalysts diffractograms. b – focus on graphitic (0 0 2) diffraction ICDD 00-058-1638. c – focus
 440 on *fcc* Ni⁰ (1 1 1) and (1 0 0) diffractions ICDD 00-004-0850. d – complete produced carbon
 441 samples diffractograms. Characteristic peaks are represented by ▼ α -Al₂O₃, ■ Ni, and ● C.
 442

443 XPS analysis was used to characterize the near surface speciation in the as-
444 activated (prior to methane splitting) and spent Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalytic layers as well
445 as in the corresponding carbon products, recovered from experiments in tubular
446 membrane reactors, without and with regeneration – Experiment 4 and Experiment 5,
447 respectively. Figure 6 depicts the obtained XPS spectra. A dominant peak in the range
448 of C 1s electron binding energy (BE) was observed for the carbon produced in both
449 experiments, Figure 6A. This asymmetric peak at *ca.* 284.5 eV is indicative of
450 conductive graphitic structures, *i.e.*- most carbon atoms display sp² hybridization. The
451 carbon bonding associated with this hybridization is characteristic of highly ordered
452 graphitic structures, while the coupled secondary peak at higher BE (+6.4 eV), the π-
453 π peak, relates to interplane bonds between graphite sheets. This suggests that graphitic
454 fibrous structures, such as tip-grown herringbone carbon nanotubes or nanofibers, or
455 base-grown multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), are being formed, as reported
456 elsewhere [35].

457 When analysing the spent catalytic surfaces from both experiments, it is seen
458 that Ni 2p, Al 2p, Si 2p, Al 2s and Si 2s peaks decrease in intensity, relative to the
459 pristine catalyst, while the C 1s peak increases, Figure 6B, indicating a degree of
460 carbon coverage over the catalyst. It must be emphasized that the sample from
461 Experiment 5 (cyclic regeneration) was collected before a final methane splitting step,
462 to allow the characterization of such carbon structures. The C 1s spectra for the spent
463 catalyst show contributions from C-C, C-O and metal-bonded carbon atoms, Figure
464 6C. The presence of C-C peaks was assigned to the presence of leftover carbon
465 allotropes, as shown in Figure 6A, but, considering the width of the observed peaks,
466 adventitious carbon species may also contribute to the signal intensity in this binding

467 energy range (two different contributions around 285 eV were identified). The C-metal
468 bonds were assigned to the formation of metal carbides or metal carbide-like structures
469 on the catalyst surface, *ca.* 283-283.5 eV. Ni carbides are unstable under the
470 characterization conditions [36]. Indeed, no carbide contribution was identified on
471 either Ni 2p (pristine and used XPS spectra available in the “Supplementary material”
472 – Figure S. 2) or Al 2p core-level spectra regions, meaning these carbide species likely
473 correspond to SiC_x, as supported by a contribution at a BE of *ca.* 99.5 eV in the Si 2p
474 core level signal, Figure 6D. Furthermore, the oxygen-bonded carbon peaks, obtained
475 at *ca.* 286.4 and 288.6 eV, have been previously correlated with Si-O-C bonding
476 [37,38], suggesting covalent linkages between the carbon products and the SiO₂
477 component of the silica-alumina catalyst support. These (near) surface silicon
478 (oxy)carbide species may provide an anchor of filamentous carbon by-products to the
479 catalyst carrier, again adding to the suggestion that a carbon tip-growth mechanism is
480 likely to occur. In the Si 2p spectra, the relative contribution of low-BE SiC species
481 was shown to increase with the implementation of selective hydrogenation
482 (Experiment 5), suggesting that cyclic hydrogenation does not revert alterations
483 suffered by the catalyst support under the high carbon chemical potential environment
484 pertaining to the methane splitting reaction. Additionally, the increase in intensity may
485 be caused by carbon removal (by interfacial hydrogenation), that left more C-bonded
486 Si atoms exposed, which in the system without cyclic regeneration (Experiment 4) are
487 covered by carbon layers thicker than Si 2p photoelectron escape depths (*ca.* >10 nm
488 [39]). Further work should be done to study these interactions and clarify the role of
489 the support on catalyst performance and mechanism selection.

492 **Figure 6** – XPS spectra of produced carbon and catalyst samples from tubular membrane reactor
 493 experiments – Experiments 4 and 5. a – C 1s and survey (corner) spectra of carbon samples from
 494 experiments without (i – Experiment 4) and with (ii – Experiment 5) regeneration. b – survey
 495 spectra of pristine (iii) and spent catalyst samples from experiments without (iv – Experiment 4)
 496 and with (v – Experiment 5) regeneration. c – C 1s spectra of spent catalyst samples from
 497 experiments without (iv – Experiment 4) and with (v – Experiment 5) regeneration. d – Si 2p
 498 spectra of spent catalyst samples from experiments without (iv – Experiment 4) and with (v –
 499 Experiment 5) regeneration.

500

501 Raman spectroscopy was used to study the structure of carbon allotropes
502 formed in tubular membrane reactors over Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃. Regions of 400 μm² square
503 were surveyed to assess the crystalline domain distribution over carbon samples, based
504 on the ratio between D (1350 cm⁻¹) and G (1550 cm⁻¹) bands of the respective spectra
505 ($\frac{I_D}{I_G}$). Raman surveys were generated by systematically analysing Raman scattering in
506 discrete points, with a regular step of 266 nm (half of the excitation wavelength), along
507 the 20 x 20 μm grid (5654 points per produced image/sample). The more crystalline a
508 structure is, the darker is the pixel that represents it.

509 Figure 7 depicts the Raman survey images and spectra of the carbon
510 crystalline structures detected from the two regions (A and D), from samples with and
511 without regeneration (Experiment 5 – Figure 7A-C and Experiment 4 – Figure 7D-F,
512 respectively); in each sample, the most crystalline structure (from the 5654 sites
513 analysed) is plotted in light blue and the subsequent darker colors represent less
514 crystalline structures. All obtained spectra are typical of defective filamentous carbon
515 ($\frac{I_D}{I_G} > 1$, with a peak 2D at *ca.* 2700 cm⁻¹), such as herringbone nanotubes or nanofibers
516 [40]. The sample from Experiment 4, without cyclic regeneration, is shown to produce
517 the most crystalline carbon (smaller $\frac{I_D}{I_G}$), and with homogeneous carbon properties:
518 highest and lowest recorded $\frac{I_D}{I_G}$ are similar - Figure 7E. The sample from Experiment
519 5, cyclic regeneration, displays less overall crystallinity and homogeneity since
520 clusters of differing $\frac{I_D}{I_G}$ ratios are observed - Figure 7A. In agreement with the
521 differences in $\frac{I_D}{I_G}$ ratios, the D+D' band (*ca.* 2900 cm⁻¹), associated with atomic
522 disorder, was seen to be much more intense in the system with cyclic regeneration.

523 Furthermore, the carbon structures detected in these clusters display G bands at higher
524 Raman shifts, compared to the unregenerated system (Figure 7B and Figure 7C). The G
525 band shift towards lower bond frequencies (higher Raman shift) indicates an increase
526 in the relative intensity of the D' band (shoulder of G peak, *ca.* 1600 cm⁻¹). This band
527 is related to the oxidation state of carbon materials, becoming larger with the presence
528 of oxygenated groups [41]. Oxygen chemisorption, which takes place after removing
529 the carbon samples from the reactor to atmospheric conditions, occurs at the carbon
530 sites with more free energy. As interfacial regeneration breaks the C-metal bonds, the
531 affected atoms should become less coordinated (more susceptible to chemisorption),
532 which justifies the detected shift of the G peak, on the sample from the Experiment 5
533 (with regeneration). Furthermore, the observed clusters display different extents in this
534 G band shift, indicating slight differences in carbon structures, among the clusters.
535 Consequently, besides tip-growth nanotubes in the collected carbon samples, other
536 types of filamentous carbon materials may coexist, such as base-grown multi-walled
537 carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs).

539 **Figure 7** - Raman surveys and spectra of the crystalline structures detected from carbon samples
 540 of tubular membrane experiments with (a to c – Experiment 5) and without (d to f – Experiment
 541 4) cyclic regeneration. The four spectra displayed for each sample are colored light blue, light
 542 grey, dark grey, and black – increasingly dark means more crystalline.

543

544 The nanomorphology of the produced carbon samples was studied by TEM.
 545 A fibrous carbon structure was observed for carbon generated from Experiment 4
 546 (without cyclic regeneration), Figure 8A and B, and carbon generated in Experiment 5
 547 (with cyclic regeneration), Figure 8C and D. These micrographs confirm the existence
 548 of pear-shaped metal particles at the tips of herringbone carbon nanotubes (tip-growth),
 549 as highlighted in Figure 8A and C. Figure 8B and D indicate the presence of MWCNT
 550 with round tips, which is a characteristic of the base-growth mechanism. This confirms
 551 that both, tip- and base-growth mechanisms coexist in the studied catalytic system.
 552 Additionally, a non-negligible fraction of catalyst detaches from the catalytic layer,
 553 indicating insufficient mechanical stability of the catalytic layer.

555 **Figure 8** – Representative TEM micrographs of carbon produced in tubular membrane
556 experiments without (a and b) and with (c and d) cyclic regeneration.

557 **4. Conclusion**

558 A set of reactor designs was built and used to study the cyclic regeneration of
559 a nickel-based catalyst for low-temperature methane splitting, at 1 bar and 550 °C. The
560 operating cycles comprehended four steps, as follows: i) production, where methane
561 was continuously fed, and hydrogen and carbon were produced; ii) a venting step using
562 nitrogen; iii) a regeneration step where hydrogen was fed; and iv) a second venting
563 step using nitrogen. The regeneration step demonstrated to extend the catalyst lifetime.
564 Depending on the system this extension could be of *ca.* 1.7 to 20 times; the supported
565 Ni/SiO₂-Al₂O₃ catalyst could be operated for a total period of *ca.* 150 h.

566 Both tip- and base-growth mechanisms are identified and the produced carbon
567 was mostly graphitic fibres/nanotubes. The catalyst seems to become available after
568 each regeneration step. However, in the supported catalytic system, the detached Ni
569 particles (tip-growth) seem to deactivate very quickly with carbon, losing their activity.
570 The coexistence of supported and detached Ni particles originates the observed very
571 high catalytic activity at the beginning of each cycle but also a continuous unreversible
572 deactivation of the catalyst, from cycle to cycle in Experiment 5. Consequently, control
573 over the dominating carbon growth mechanism is required to further increase the
574 regenerability via cyclic interfacial hydrogenation.

575 Finally, the detection of near-surface silicon (oxy)carbide species suggests a
576 covalent anchoring of at least a part of the grown carbon nanostructures to the ceramic
577 support of the catalyst. Such anchoring may be formed during the carbon nucleation

578 stage, at the interface between the metal nanoparticles and the $\text{SiO}_2\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$, as required
579 for the tip-growth mechanism. Further research must be done to understand the
580 formation of these carbides and assess their role in controlling carbon growth
581 mechanisms.

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Table 1 – The reactors' main characteristics and the corresponding catalytic activity and stability.

<i>Experiment</i>	<i>Material</i>	<i>Reactor</i>	<i>Deposition</i>	<i>Area cm²</i>	<i>Loading mg·cm⁻²</i>	<i>Peak activity g_{H₂}·g_{Ni}⁻¹·h⁻¹</i>	<i>Time on stream h</i>	<i>Total H₂ production g_{H₂}·g_{Ni}⁻¹</i>	<i>Total C production g_C·g_{Ni}⁻¹</i>
Experiment 1 <i>Cyclic</i>	Ni-bulk	Planar (A)	Screen- printing	4	10	0.08	4.8	0.20	0.60
Experiment 2 <i>Continuous</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ - Al ₂ O ₃	Wall- coated Tubular (B)	Dip-coating	22	10	0.17	14	2.3	6.9
Experiment 3 <i>Cyclic</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ - Al ₂ O ₃	Wall- coated Tubular (B)	Dip-coating	22	10	0.17	19	3.0	9.1
Experiment 4 <i>Continuous</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ - Al ₂ O ₃	Tubular Membra ne (C)	Dip-coating	16.5	19	1.0	50	32	95
Experiment 5 <i>Cyclic</i>	Ni/SiO ₂ - Al ₂ O ₃	Tubular Membra ne (C)	Dip-coating	16.5	19	1.0	100	40	120

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Adelio Mendes has patent #WO2020121287 issued to University of Porto. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.